

Mental Toughness and Decision Making Between Cricket and Football Players: A Comparison

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Introduction:

Psychology is important as it is concerned with the study of behavior and mental processes and at the same time, it is also applied to many different things in human life. Through psychology, we are able to understand and determine how the mind and body of an individual works. Mental toughness is having the natural or developing psychological edge that enables you to normally cope better than your opponents with the many demands (competition, training lifestyle) that sports places on a performance and specifically to be more consistent and better than your opponents in remaining determined, focused, confidence and in control under pressure (Jones et al 2002) mentally tough competition also have the unique ability to exert control over the varying demands placed upon them in training and their personal life. Lopez (1977) has defined a decision as a judgment, a final resolution of a conflict of needs, means or goals; and a commitment to action made in face of uncertainty, complexity and even irrationally. Therefore decision making is an important part of all science-based professions, where specialists apply their knowledge in a given area to making informed decisions. Decision-making is an integral part of everyday life and level of self-confidence is related to the time it takes to make a decision. Myers (1962) indicated that a person's decision-making process

depends to a significant degree on their cognitive style; as in most decision-making situations, an individual faces different degrees of uncertainty. In probabilistic terms, this situation is called ambiguity.

Decision making is the process of sufficiently reducing uncertainty and doubt about alternatives to allow a reasonable choice to be made from among them. The present study aimed to determine the difference in self-confidence and decision making between psychology and physical education students.

Objectives of The Study;

1. To establish the difference between cricket and football players on the variable Mental Toughness.
2. To establish the difference between cricket and football players on the variable decision making.

Hypotheses of The Study:

H01: Indicated that there would have been no significant difference between cricket and football players on the variable Mental Toughness.

H02: Indicated that there would have been no significant difference between cricket and football players on the variable decision making.

Materials And Methods:

Sample: A total of eighty (N = 50) male subjects out of which twenty-five (N = 25) Cricket players and twenty-five (N = 25) football players from Department of Physical Education BHU, Varanasi were randomly selected for the collection of data. The age of the subjects was ranged between 19 to 25 years.

Tools: Mental Toughness was measured by applying Mental Toughness questionnaire prepared by Dr, Alan Golberg and decision making was measured by applying decision making questionnaire prepared by French et al. (1993).

Instrumentation:

The questionnaire was measured the following five dimensions.

Rebound Ability: For rebound ability the response of question 3 & 6 is "Yes" while response of question 1, 4, 5 is "NO".

Ability to Handle Pressure: For ability to handle pressure, the response of question 7 & 11 is "YES" while 8,9,10 and 12 is "NO".

Concentration: For concentration, the response question 17 is "YES" while 13,14,15,16 and 18 is "NO".

Confidence: For confidence, 19, 21& 22 is "YES" while 20, 23 and 24 is "NO"

Motivation: For motivation, the response of question 25, 26, 27, 29 & 30 is "YES" while 28 is "NO".

Over all scoring: A score of 26-30 indicate strength in overall mental toughness. Score of 23-25 indicate average to moderate skill in mental toughness. Score of 22 below means that

individual need to start putting more time into the mental training area.

The decision-making questionnaire consisted of twenty one (N = 21) items measuring the decision making. The respondents were required to record their responses in six categories, very infrequently or never, infrequently, quite infrequently, quite frequently, frequently and very frequently or always. The scoring of each of the items was as follows; very infrequently or never = 1, infrequently = 2, quite infrequently = 3, quite frequently = 4, frequently and very frequently or always = 6. There was no right or wrong answers in this questionnaire. There was none allocated for the completion of both the questionnaires but the subjects were instructed not taken too much time over any questions. The questionnaires were distributed to the respondents along with the writing material. After the completion of the questionnaires, questionnaires were collected and checked that no response was left unanswered.

Statistical Analysis:

The "t" test was applied to find out the difference between mean scores of cricket and football players on the variables Mental Toughness and decision making. The level of significance was set at 0.05 for testing of hypotheses.

Results:

The results of Mental Toughness and decision making questionnaires of cricket and football players are presented in tables and interpretations are given accordingly.

Table I: Comparison of mean scores with regard to 'Mental Toughness' between Cricket players and Football players

Group	Mean	SD	SEM	t-value	P-value
Cricket players	62.600	10.420	2.084	1.556	.126
Football players	57.560	12.393	2.478		

^aSignificant at 0.05, table value = 2.01 (df = 48).

Table 1 showed that comparisons on the variable of Mental Toughness between cricket players and football players. The mean values of Cricket players and Football players were found to be 62.600 and 57.560, respectively. The standard deviation of Cricket players and Football players were 10.420 and 12.393 respectively, the standard error of mean scores came out to be 2.084 and 2.478 respectively. The 't' value of 1.556 was found to be insignificant as the tabulated value was 2.01 at 0.05 level of significance with degree of freedom of 48 and while comparing the two mean values it shows that Cricket players have performed better on the

variable 'Mental Toughness' than their counterpart Football players. (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Graphical presentation of mean scores with regard to 'Mental Toughness' between Cricket players and Football players

Table II: Comparison of mean scores with regard to 'Decision Making' between Cricket players and Football players.

Group	Mean	S D	SEM	t-value	P-value
Cricket players	27.760	1.920	.384	2.949	.005
Football players	25.960	2.371	.474		

'Significant at 0.05, table value = 2.01 (df = 48)

Table 2 showed that comparisons on the variable of 'decision making' between Cricket players and Football players. The mean values of Cricket players and Football players were found to be 27.760 and 25.960, respectively. The standard deviation of Cricket players and Football players were 1.920 and 2.371 respectively, the standard error of mean scores came out to be .384 and .474 respectively.

Figure 2. Graphical presentation of mean scores with regard to 'decision making' between Cricket players and Football players

The 't' value 2.949 was found to be significant as the tabulated value was 2.01 at 0.05 level of significance with degree of freedom 48 and while comparing the two mean values it shows that Cricket players have performed better on the variable 'decision making' than their counterpart Football players. (Figure 2)

Discussion:

It is evident from the above findings that significant differences were found between Cricket players and Football players on the variable of decision making as the obtained t-value 2.949 was found higher than the table value 2.01. The results revealed that Cricket players

have better decision making level as compared to the Football players. The results might be attributed to their practical environment includes different nature of game. As per the obtained t-value 2.949 was found significant difference between Cricket players and Football players indicate that the null hypothesis (H₀) in regard to decision making is rejected. Flaming et al. (2010) found that significant difference between Philippines and United States students on the variable decision making. The results with regard to the variable of Mental Toughness between Cricket players and Football players were found statistically insignificant as the obtained t-value 1.556 was found lower than the table value 2.01. The results indicate that Cricket players have high mental toughness level as compared to their counterpart Football players. The obtained t-value 1.556 was found insignificant difference between Cricket players and Football players indicated that null hypothesis (H₀) in regard to mental toughness is also accepted.

Conclusion:

The results revealed significant difference with regard to variable decision making between Cricket players and Football players. However, the results with regard to the variable mental toughness were found statistically insignificant between Cricket players and Football players. Cricket players have better mental toughness and

decision making level as compared to their counterpart Football players.

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